

Electro-Chromatography in the Study of Ions. Estimation of Copper and Silver by Photo-electric Scanner

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Paper electrophoretic technique has been utilised for the separation and direct estimation of (i) Cu and (ii) Ag ions. Cu can be effectively separated from Ag, Hg, Pb and Cd respectively and Ag from Hg, Pb, Cu, Bi and Cd respectively, when the binary mixtures of these ions are subjected to paper electrophoresis using different electrolytes. The separated Cu or Ag band can be directly quantitatively estimated by the photoelectric scanner.

DIRECT photometry after paper electrophoretic separation of small amount of migrant can be utilised as the rapid method¹⁻⁴ for determination of the migrant content in the mixture. A drop of copper nitrate solution and a drop of silver nitrate solution separately subjected to paper electrophoresis using Na₂ EDTA as carrier electrolyte. The zone of the migrated silver ion is located by spraying with ammonium sulphide and copper ion by spraying with rubeanic acid and then an attempt has been made to estimate these ions from the band with photo-electric scanner.

Experimental

A simple form of apparatus as shown in Fig. 1 is used for the experiment. It consists of one milliammeter, one voltmeter, a sliding rheostat, two Pt-electrodes, two small glass tumblers, each connected with two co-axial pyrex tubes, the inner tubes having small holes on the side, a plastic sheet (with two small

round holes for two terminals of the voltmeter and two straight slits) to cover the two small glass tumblers containing the electrolyte; an inverted T shaped plastic stand to be placed in the middle of

the plastic sheet in between the two slits; a cover to enclose the set and Carl Schleicher and Schull filter-paper strip of size 3.9 cm × 40 cm.

The filterpaperstrip is placed on the inverted T shaped stand while its two ends pass through the slits and touch the electrolyte in the two glass tumblers. The co-axial tubes and the glass tumblers are filled with the electrolyte, so that the electric current can pass easily from the tubes to the solution in the glass tumblers. The two Pt electrodes are in the inner tubes, the holes of which are plugged with glass wools. The electrodes are thereby surrounded by a labyrinth system lest either dissolved or gaseous electrolytic products should reach the paperstrip.

A drop of copper nitrate solution (prepared from electrolytic copper containing 0.13 mg of copper per 0.01 ml) and a drop of silver nitrate solution (containing 0.1 mg of silver per 0.01 ml prepared from silver nitrate, (Anal B.D.H.) are taken separately at the top region (marked with a pencil) of different Carl Schleicher and Schull filterpaper strip (each 3.9 cm × 40 cm) moistened carefully with 0.05 molar Na₂ EDTA (Titriplex III of E. Merck) and subjected to electrophoresis for 5 hr under a potential difference of 150 volts. pH of the electrolyte before electrophoresis is 4.54, and after electrophoresis 4.57 at the cathode and 4.38 at the anode respectively.

The experiment is then repeated with 0.01 ml of copper nitrate solution containing 0.26 mg and 0.39 mg of copper respectively and with 0.01 ml of silver nitrate solution containing 0.05 mg and 0.15 mg of silver respectively. After the run, each paperstrip is taken out, air dried and the copper band is then located with 0.5% solution of rubeanic acid of B.D.H. in alcohol and again dried; while the silver band (comet shaped tailing back to zero) is located with chemically pure ammonium sulphide solution and again dried. The strips are then rendered transparent by immersing in xylene, a liquid having the same refractive index as the cellulose fibre.

These are then freed from air and are placed between two glass slides and scanned with the help of a photoelectric scanner.

From the data of the extinction values of the band the graph is plotted as shown in Figs. 2A and 2B.

Fig. 2A. Estimation of Copper by photo-electric scanner. 0.13 mg of Cu corresponds to area of 1040 sq.mm. shown in the Curve No. 1. 0.26 mg. of Cu corresponds to area of 2240 sq.mm. shown in the Curve No. 2. 0.39 mg of Cu corresponds to area of 3280 sq.mm. shown in the Curve No. 3.

Fig. 2B. Estimation of Ag by photo-electric scanner. 0.05 mg of Ag corresponds to area of 444 sq.mm. shown in the Curve No. A. 0.10 mg of Ag corresponds to area of 880 sq.mm. shown in the Curve No. B. 0.15 mg. of Ag corresponds to area of 1368 sq.mm. shown in the Curve No. C.

The area of each diagram is then measured with the aid of a planimeter and recorded in Table 1.

TABLE I

Electrophoregram containing	Corresponding figure	Area of the characteristic curve in mm with the aid of a planimeter
0.13 mg of Cu	1	1040
0.26 " "	2	2240
0.39 " "	3	3280
0.05 " Ag	A	444
0.1 " "	B	880
0.15 " "	C	1368

The area under the curves are distinctly proportional to the copper and the silver content and the error lies within $\pm 5\%$.

This communication reports that copper can be quantitatively separated from Ag with 0.05M Na₂ EDTA, from Bi and Cd with 0.1N and 0.05N HCl respectively; from Hg with 0.4N NH₄Cl, from Pb with 1N Tartaric acid. Similarly Ag can be separated quantitatively from Hg, Pb, Bi and Cu with 0.05M Na₂ EDTA and from Cd with 0.1N KNO₃ solution.

Nitrate solution of (i) Cu-Ag containing 0.13 mg of Cu and 0.13 mg of Ag, (ii) Cu-Hg and Cu-Pb each containing 0.26 mg of Cu and 0.26 mg of Hg and 0.26 mg of Pb and (iii) Cu-Bi and Cu-Cd each containing 0.39 mg of each ion per 0.01 ml of the mixtures, are used for each electrophoretic separation. Band of copper in each case is then located with rubenic acid and the other bands with ammonium sulphide solution.

Nitrate solution of Ag-Hg, Ag-Pb (containing per 0.01 ml, 0.05 mg of Ag, Hg and Pb respectively), Ag-Bi, Ag-Cu and Ag-Cd (containing per 0.01 ml, 0.15 mg of Ag, Bi, Cu and Cd respectively) are used for the experiments.

For each electrophoretic run 0.01 ml of the mixture is used. After the experiment each paperstrip is taken out, air dried and the bands are then located with chemically pure ammonium sulphide and again the paper is dried. Each strip is then rendered transparent by xylene and each copper and silver band is then scanned by photoelectric scanner.

Separation sequences and position (in m.m.) of the migrating zone (front and rear) from the point of application after 5 hrs' run under a potential difference of 150 volts are given below their respective names, in the Table 2. In the table the direction of the movement of the cations and anions are indicated by the signs '-' and '+' and the starting point ':'. An ion which leaves 'Ghost spot' at the point of application is included in the parenthesis.

The following interesting facts have emerged from the investigation concerning the role of the carrier electrolytes :

(i) Cu, Hg, Pb and Bi form anionic complex in 0.05M Na₂ EDTA and moves towards the anode, (ii) Bi⁺⁺⁺ in 0.1N HCl forms anionic complex, (iii) Hg⁺⁺ in 0.4N NH₄Cl moves towards the anode due to formation of an ionic complex and (iv) Cd in 0.05N HCl and Pb in 1N tartaric acid move towards the cathode as simple cations. Na₂ EDTA (0.05M), HCl (0.1N) and NH₄Cl (0.05N) act both as complexing agent and as carrier electrolyte, whereas HCl (0.05N) and Tartaric acid (1N) behave simply as carrier electrolyte.

The extinction values of the copper and silver spots are determined separately and plotted as shown in Fig. 3A and 3B. The area of each curve is measured with the acid of a planimeter and the area of respective curves are recorded as shown in the Table 3.

The area of each curve is directly proportional to the metal content and the error lies within $\pm 5\%$. For correct and reproducible results, upto 0.4 mg

TABLE 2

Carrier electrolyte	pH of the carrier electrolyte		Binary Mixture	Separation sequences and position (in mm) of the ions	
	before electrolysis	after cathode anode compartment			
Na ₂ EDTA (0.05M)	4.54	4.57,4.38	Cu-Ag	-(Ag) : -8 to 3,	Cu+ 33 to 54
HCl (0.1N)	1.04	1.04&1.02	Cu-Bi	-Cu : -26 to -50,	Bi+ 6 to 22
HCl (0.05N)	1.36	1.38&1.38	Cu-Cd	-Cu : -52 to -86,	Cd :+ -22 to -38
Ammonium chloride (0.4N)	5.65	5.99&3.02	Cu-Hg	-Cu : -20 to -45,	Hg+ 40 to 60
Tartaric acid (1N)	1.61	1.62&1.63	Cu-Pb	-Pb : -59 to -78,	Cu :+ -33 to -57
Na ₂ EDTA (0.05M)	4.54	4.57&4.38	Ag-Hg	-(Ag) : -8 to 3,	Hg+ 29 to 45
"	"	"	Ag-Pb	-(Ag) : -5 to 4	Pb+ 6 to 23
"	"	"	Ag-Bi	-(Ag) : -4 to 4	Bi+ 13 to 34
"	"	"	Ag-Cu	-(Ag) : -2.1 to 3.5	Cu+ 7 to 22
KNO ₃ (0.1N)	6.79	7.10&2.68	Ag-Cd	-Cd : -70 to -85	(Ag)+ -20 to 5

Fig. 3A. Estimation of Copper by photometry after electrophoretic separation from mixtures. 0.13 mg of Cu corresponds to area of 1080 sq.mm. shown in the Curve "a". 0.26 mg of Cu corresponds to area of 2112 sq.mm. shown in the Curve "b". 0.39 mg of Cu corresponds to area of 3400 sq.mm. shown in the Curve "c". 0.26 mg of Cu corresponds to area of 2120 sq.mm. shown in the Curve "d". 0.39 mg. of Cu corresponds to area of 3270 sq.mm. shown in the Curve "e".

Fig. 3B. Estimation of Silver by photometry after electrophoretic separation from mixtures. 0.05 mg of Ag corresponds to area 440 sq.mm. shown in the Curve A'. 0.05 mg of Ag corresponds to area 432 sq.mm. shown in the Curve A''. 0.15 mg of Ag corresponds to area 1380 sq.mm. shown in the Curve C'. 0.15 mg of Ag corresponds to area 1376 sq.mm. shown in the Curve C''. 0.15 mg of Ag corresponds to area 1320 sq.mm. shown in the Curve C'''.

TABLE 3

Electropherogram containing	Corresponding figure	Area of the characteristic curve in mm with the aid of a planimeter
0.13 mg of Cu	a	1080
0.26 "	b	2112
0.39 "	c	3400
0.26 "	d	2120
0.39 "	e	3270
0.05 mg of Ag	A'	440
0.05 "	A''	432
0.15 "	C''	1380
0.15 "	C'	1376
0.15 "	C'''	1320

of Cu (0.01 ml) and 0.15 mg of Ag (0.01 ml) can be subjected to paper electrophoresis.

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